

diseased plants in the field, except those infected at later growth stages. No yellowish-white specks — the typical symptom of rice dwarf virus (RDV) disease — were observed on the leaf blades.

The dwarfing, caused by incomplete emergence of the younger leaves, was particularly conspicuous in the plants inoculated at earlier growth stages.

The galls or vein-swellings appeared on the undersurface of the leaf blades and on the upper parts of the leaf sheaths.

The galls were light green and rather translucent at first, but later became brownish. They were more abundant in early infected plants, some of whose leaves had more than 10 galls. The galls varied from 0.4 to 0.5 mm in width and 0.4 to 8 mm in length.

The discoloration of infected plants was another characteristic symptom. Infected hills were easily recognized by their dark-green color in the field and in the transmission test.

Another minor symptom was the twisting of the tips of newly developed leaves — supposedly because of an alternating, uneven growth of the leaf blades on both sides of the midrib.

The plant's leaf tip began to dry; eventually, the entire plant dried and died.

Spherical particles about 65 nm in diameter (vs 70 nm in RDV), were always observed in the leaf-dip preparations of gall dwarf-infected tissues (photo 1). They were more abundant in the preparations from galls than in those from nongall leaf tissues. The particles had a capsid-like structure. Ultrathin sections showed virus particles in the phloem cells of the diseased plant (photo 2).

The clumping technique was used in an immunoelectron microscopic test to study the serological relationship of the particles with RDV. Particles that consistently appeared in preparations of grids with RDV and RDV antiserum were many and clumped while those observed on the grids with specimens infected with rice gall dwarf disease and RDV antiserum were few and dispersed.

Among the rice virus diseases, rice black-streaked dwarf and rice ragged stunt have a symptomatology similar to

1. Electron micrograph showing virus particles in a dip preparation from the sample infected with rice gall dwarf disease.

2. Electron micrograph showing virus particles in a phloem cell of a rice plant infected with rice gall dwarf disease.

that of rice gall dwarf disease. But rice gall dwarf induces the formation of numerous small galls; the other diseases produce a few elongated swellings of the veins. It is difficult to distinguish rice gall dwarf disease from rice ragged stunt in the field. Plants with rice gall dwarf disease, however, have no ragged leaf blades and their leaves become dark green unlike those of plants infected with ragged stunt.

The causal agent of rice gall disease is presumably a virus with spherical

particles about 65 nm in diameter, capsid-like in structure. Three rice viruses are reported among the plant reovirus group — RDV, rice black-streaked dwarf virus, and rice ragged stunt. Only the virus particles of RDV have a capsid-like structure. But immunoelectron microscopic examination revealed that the particles associated with rice gall dwarf disease are not serologically related to RDV, suggesting that rice gall dwarf is a new virus disease. ■

Chlorotic streak, a new virus disease of rice

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Since 1978, we have observed a new virus disease of rice on the CRRRI farm and in farmers' fields surrounding Cuttack. In the field the disease occurs in patches (Fig. 1) ranging in size from about 1 to 10 m². Its severity decreases from the center to the outer edges of the affected patch. The diseased plants in the center are much more severely damaged than those on the edge, indicating that a slow-moving agent spreads the disease.

In artificially inoculated plants, the symptoms were stunted plant growth (Fig. 2), chlorotic streaking, striping, or mottling (Fig. 3) of the newly emerging leaves; difficult emergence of leaves and panicles; and brown discoloration and grain sterility. Chlorotic streaks also appeared on the leaf sheaths. Other

1. Diseased patch of rice chlorotic streak in farmers' field. The circle represents the diseased patch.

symptoms observed occasionally were twisting, curling, crinkling, blunt edges, wavy margin, ragging, tearing, raised blisters, rough surface, and dark green color of the leaves; swelling and irregular

2. Healthy and diseased plants of IR26. The infected plant is stunted.

3. Chlorotic streaks and mottling on the leaves, the characteristic symptoms of the disease.

growth of the veins; and stimulation of new tillers. Nodal branching and aerial root formation were also observed. The symptoms varied widely among varieties and ages of infected plants. Some infected plants recovered from the disease.

Both persistent and nonpersistent attempts at transmission by *Nephotettix virescens*, *N. nigropictus* and *Nilaparvata lugens* and by mechanical means and the seed were unsuccessful. The constant association of the rice mealy bug

Heterococcus rehi (*Ripersia oryzae*) with the disease in the field encouraged us to conduct transmission tests with the insect. In all three tests, each involving 100 test seedlings, transmission with the mealy bug was positive. About 30-40% of the seedlings of Jaya and IR26 are infected when each seedling was inoculated by three infective nymphs; none of the check seedlings showed symptoms. Transmission appeared to be nonpersistent. The transmission pattern, virus-vector relationships and structure of the virus

are being investigated in greater detail.

Previously reported virus and mycoplasma diseases of rice are transmitted by leafhoppers, planthoppers, and beetles, and through mechanical inoculation, but not by the rice mealy bug. The symptoms of the new virus disease are distinctly different from those of the reported diseases. We have therefore named the disease *Chlorotic streak* on the basis of its characteristic symptoms. ■

Ecology, epidemiology, and supervised control of rice brown leaf spot

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The ecology, epidemiology, and supervised control of brown leaf spot of rice caused by *Drechslera oryzae* has been studied in Karnataka. The following observations on brown spot epidemiology were made:

1. The glume blotch phase of the disease, which is the most serious, causes large yield losses.
2. The disease is not strictly seedborne in the sense that seedborne inoculum does not cause the usual disease symptoms such as leaf spotting and glume blotching.

3. The seedborne inoculum causes pre-emergence death of the seedlings only.
4. The pathogen is not soil borne; it survives only 4-6 weeks in puddled or semidry soil. It is highly aerobic and subject to biological antagonism in the soil.
5. The perfect state of the fungus was not found in nature, nor were any collateral hosts found although about 50 grass species were examined.
6. The leaf spots do not sporulate. Sporulation occurred, however, when the leaves were treated with warm water, indicating an inhibitory, water-soluble component in the spot. The leaf spots do not supply the inoculum for glume infection.
7. All the straw samples collected

from several straw ricks in farmers' holdings yielded viable *D. oryzae*.

8. Studies using a suction-type volumetric spore trap for 365 days indicated year-round presence of *D. oryzae* spores in the atmosphere.

9. The number of such spores varied seasonally. The lowest number was 500,000/liter of air in February-March and the highest, 17,000,000/liter of air in November.

10. There was diurnal variation in spore numbers. The maximum was from 0300 to 0900 hours and the minimum, from 1500 to 2100 hours.

11. Seed treatment with hot water does not ensure disease control, and spraying the crop at any stage before heading has no practical value.